

Comparison of three BERT language models for Automatic Misogyny Identification on Italian tweets

Cristian Santini

Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge, University of Bologna

Abstract

Automatic Misogyny Identification (AMI) is a new task in Natural Language Processing that belongs to the domain of Text Classification and it has been proposed for the first time by Fersini et al. at the IberEval 2018 evaluation campaign¹. In this research paper we will address the problem of misogyny identification on Italian tweets by comparing the performances of three pre-trained BERT models for Italian: ALBERTo (Polignano et al., 2019), GilBERTo and UmBERTo. This paper reports how, after fine-tuning these models for binary classification, all three models were able to achieve state-of-the-art performances by beating the results of the models evaluated in the AMI Evalita 2018 campaign².

Introduction

During last years hate against women on online environments has appeared as a relevant issue: according to recent studies, in Europe 1 in 10 women has experienced some kind of cyber violence since the age of 15 (Van der Wilk, 2018) and, as reported by the American Online Hate and Harassment Report (2020), 12% of the people who reported online harassment were subject to some type of sexual harassment and most of them were women. Misogynistic behaviour, defined as the hate or prejudice against women, can be manifested through language in numerous ways and, in this context, the Automatic Misogyny Identification shared task was proposed first at IberEval 2018 (Spanish and English) (Fersini et al., 2018) and later at Evalita 2018 (Italian and English) (Caselli et al., 2018). Automatic Misogyny Identification is an umbrella term under which a number of text classification tasks falls. For this study we focused on the main task of targeting misogynistic behaviour in Italian tweets by means of a binary classification: 1 if the tweet presents a misogynistic behaviour, 0 if it doesn't.

Nowadays, there are a number of systems and algorithms to automatically classify text given a number of output labels; among the most successful, for sure it has to be mentioned BERT (Devlin et al., 2018). BERT, which stands for Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers, is a

¹ <https://amiibereval2018.wordpress.com/>

² <https://amievalita2018.wordpress.com/>

Transformer-based model for representing language introduced by Google in 2018. BERT is designed to pre-train deep bidirectional representations from unlabeled text by jointly taking in consideration both left and right context of each word, given a sentence. Given its architecture, BERT can be easily and rapidly fine-tuned on a wide variety of natural language processing tasks, such as text classification, question answering, entity recognition, etc., reaching state-of-the-art performances.

For the misogyny identification task, we decided to fine-tune three pre-trained BERT models for Italian, freely available on the net: AIBERTO³, GilBERTo⁴ and UmBERTo⁵. AIBERTO (Polignano et al., 2019) is a BERT language understanding model pre-trained on Italian social-media language, while UmBERTo and GilBERTo are two Italian language models based on RoBERTa (Liu et al., 2019), a retraining of BERT with improved training methodology. For fine-tuning and testing the models we used the dataset made available by the AMI Evalita 2018 campaign, consisting of Italian tweets labelled with misogyny value (either 1 or 0). Our study adopted the same metric proposed by the campaign, the accuracy metric, to evaluate the models and to compare their results with the models officially ranked.

BERT and related works

BERT is a deep neural network architecture released by Google in 2018 aimed at developing powerful language understanding models by means of deep representations of words, also called word embeddings. Word embeddings are one of the biggest revolutions in NLP of the last decade. Like embeddings are low dimensional representations of a point in a higher dimensional vector space, word embeddings are dense vector representations of words in lower dimensional space. This technique is driven by the assumptions of distributional semantics, a theory by which the meaning of a word can be analyzed by looking at its distributional properties across large samples of texts.

The term *word embeddings* was first introduced in the NLP community by Bengio et al. in 2003 but became very popular in 2013 with the release of Word2Vec (Mikolov et al., 2013), a set of model architectures aimed at developing language models by extracting word embeddings from large corpora. Since then, a wide variety of models sprout out, exploiting the intuition of word embeddings, and they demonstrated their robustness in a number of NLP tasks. Their effectiveness is pretty easy to explain, since with word embeddings it's possible to model the semantic importance of a word in a geometrical space and thus perform mathematical operations on it.

³ <https://github.com/marcopoli/AIBERTO-it>

⁴ <https://github.com/idb-ita/GilBERTo>

⁵ <https://github.com/musixmatchresearch/umberto>

However, in the last years we assisted to new innovations in the field of distributional semantics, such as contextualized word embeddings. This type of technique, introduced with the ELMo architecture (Peters et al., 2018), focused on the possibility of creating distinct representations of the same word (e.g. embeddings) for different contexts in which they occur: this allowed, for example, to create different representations for homonyms. In their research paper, Peters et al. trained ELMo, a bi-directional LSTM, on a large corpus with the aim of developing a language model by making him to predict the previous and the next word of a token. The way ELMo accomplished that task was by producing bidirectional word embeddings which were jointly conditioned both on the left and on the right context.

Nonetheless another crucial innovation that we need to tackle before talking about BERT is Transformers (Vaswani et al., 2017). Introduced by Google in 2017, Transformers represented a revolution in NLP by introducing the concept of *attention*. In a deep neural network, an attention mechanism helps a hidden layer to have a complete picture of the input sentence while it processes a certain word. Transformers were introduced as a solution for machine translation problems and revealed more effective in modeling long term dependencies than other models (like rNN and LSTM) and more efficient in reducing training times.

BERT takes advantage of these two innovations by creating bi-directional representations of words by means of a deep neural network architecture where each hidden layer, also called encoder, has a self-attention layer. Given this architecture, BERT is characterized by two main features:

- as ELMo, it provides context-sensitive representation of words (e.g. different word representations for homonyms);
- given the intuition on which Transformers are based, BERT processes each word by taking in consideration the information of the whole sentence, while different models, such as LSTMs, read the input sequentially.

Thus, BERT revealed as one of the most promising innovations in NLP, introducing a new tool to pretrain powerful language understanding models with effectiveness and efficiency. In order to get bidirectional contextual embedding, in their research paper Devlin et al. trained BERT on two different tasks: language masking and next sentence prediction. However, just adding one output layer on top, each pre-trained model can be easily fine-tuned in a wide-variety of NLP tasks, such as question answering and text-classification, reaching state-of-the-art performances.

Since 2018, a number of BERT-based language models sprout out. AIBERTO is a BERT-based Italian language understanding model. More specifically, AIBERTO is focused on Italian Social Media language (Polignano et al., 2018) and was trained on TWITA (Basile et al., 2018), a large Italian corpus of tweets. AIBERTO is an uncased model with 768 hidden units, 12 layers and 12

attention heads. To demonstrate its robustness, AIBERTo was evaluated by the authors on the EVALITA 2016 task SENTIPOLC (SENTiment POLarity Classification) obtaining state of the art results in subjectivity, polarity and irony detection on Italian tweets (Polignano et al., 2018).

GilBERTo and UmBERTo are Italian language models based on Facebook RoBERTa architecture (Liu et al., 2019). These models were trained on large Italian corpora crawled from the web. Both the models have 768 hidden units, 12 layers and 12 attention heads and reached state-of-the-art results in Part-Of-Speech tagging and Named Entity Recognition. However, while GilBERTo is available only as an uncased model, UmBERTo is available both as cased and uncased. For this research, we fine-tuned the cased version of UmBERTo, to see if this type of models shows different results in misogyny identification.

Automatic Misogyny Identification

Automatic Misogyny Identification is a new shared task proposed at Evalita 2018, both for Italian and English (Fersini et al., 2018). Automatic Misogyny Identification was conceived as an umbrella term under which a number of text classification tasks were included. The AMI shared task of Evalita 2018 had as a main goal to distinguish misogynous contents from non-misogynous ones, to categorize misogynistic behaviour and finally to classify the target of a tweet.

Misogynous	Text
Misogynous	Drink your lemonade and cry, bi**h
Non-misogynous	Online seller, pls display price you cu*t!

Table 1: an example of misogynous and non-misogynous tweets

The task was divided into a number of subtasks, but for our research purpose we only took in consideration the problem of distinguishing misogynous tweets from non-misogynous ones for Italian. In this research we report how we trained and tested our BERT-based models on the same dataset of the shared task of Evalita 2018. The official metric proposed for the subtask was the raw accuracy of the system’s predictions:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{True Positives} + \text{True Negatives}}{\text{All Samples}}$$

A number of systems were evaluated in the campaign. All were compared to a baseline, which consisted in an algorithm based on Support Vector Machine trained on a unigram representation of tweets. The baseline reached an accuracy of 0.83 while the most accurate system evaluated was

bakarov.c.run2, which reached an accuracy of 0.844. This system, realized by Bakarov (Bakarov, 2018) from Huawei Technologies, was based on using TF-IDF n-gram word features and a Logistic Regression. Other systems evaluated were based on SVMs, Decision Trees ensembles (e.g. Random Forest) and dense neural networks.

Dataset

An Italian dataset of tweets was provided for research purposes by the AMI Evalita 2018 organizers. The dataset was collected in three ways (Fersini et al., 2018):

- Selecting tweets by searching for the presence of representative keywords (e.g. *pu****a*, *tr**a*, for Italian);
- Monitoring of potential victims' accounts, e.g. *gamergate victims and public feminist women*;
- Downloading the history of identified misogynists, i.e. *explicitly declared hate against women on their Twitter profiles*.

After collection, the corpus was manually annotated by a group of experts according to three parameters: *Misogyny* (Misogyny vs Not Misogyny); *Misogynistic Category* (Discredit, Derailing, Dominance, Sexual Harassment & Threats of Violence, Stereotype & Objectification); *Target* (Active vs Passive). Both the training and the testing data has been provided as tab-separated, according to 4 values:

- **id** denotes a unique identifier of the tweet (e.g. an integer).
- **text** represents the tweet text
- **misogynous** defines if the tweet is misogynous or not misogynous; it takes values as 1 if the tweet is misogynous, 0 if the tweet is not misogynous.
- **misogyny category** denotes the type of misogynistic behaviour, according to the aforementioned categories.
- **target** denotes the subject of the misogynous; it takes values as active, passive or 0, if the tweet is not misogynous

For the task of misogyny identification through binary classification we only took in consideration the **misogynous** values, either 1 or 0, with respect to the text. The dataset for Italian consists of 4000 tweets in the train set and 1000 tweets in the test set. Moreover, for the training procedure, we split the train dataset into training set and validation set. The percentages for splitting the train dataset were the following: 90% training (3600), 10% validation (400). According to the misogynous label, the table below reports the distribution of misogynous labels.

	Training	Testing
Misogynous	1828 (46%)	512 (51%)
Non-misogynous	2172 (54%)	488 (49%)

Table 2: distribution of misogynous labels for the Italian dataset

Setup

The models were trained using the Pytorch Transformers module. All training phases were run on Google Colaboratory, by using the free GPU provided by the platform. The pre-trained models were downloaded from the Transformers API. For fine-tuning, we recycled an unofficial Python script made available on the web by Chris McCormick⁶.

Data preprocessing

Each BERT model needs a little bit of text preprocessing in order to be fed with text in the training phase. The text should be split into tokens and tokens transformed into integers (unique ids). In addition, special tokens should be added: [SEP] for the ending of a sentence, [CLS] for the starting of a sentence, [PAD] for padding, and [UNK] for unknown tokens. Furthermore, BERT processes texts of equal length, so sequences of tokens in input should be padded to a max length.

Since the maximum tweet length in our train set was 98, we padded each tweet to a max length of 128. In order to batch input sequences together and feed the data to the neural network, we also took in consideration the attention mask, which is an optional argument when batching sequences together that indicates to the model which tokens should be attended to, and which should not (e.g. [PAD] tokens).

Training

For fine-tuning the models in order to perform well on the aforementioned binary classification task, I used the *BertForSequenceClassification* class of Pytorch, which adds to the pre-trained models a linear layer on top for classification/regression tasks. For a matter of clarity, we want to briefly describe how a BERT model is fine-tuned. In the training phase, the model receives as input the training data split in batches, each of them containing as tensors a subset of tweets converted to sequences of input ids, with the corresponding attention mask and misogyny values. As input data is fed into a forward procedure, the entire pre-trained BERT model and the additional untrained classification layer is trained on predicting labels for unseen data. The model processes the data by

⁶ <https://mccormickml.com/2019/07/22/BERT-fine-tuning/>

means of a forward pass that computes predictions for the possible labels (e.g. 1 for misogyny, 0 for no misogyny) for each batch. After making predictions, the model calculates the loss on the true labels via a Cross Entropy Loss function; then, a backward pass is performed to calculate the gradient, given the loss on the training batch, and then the model’s weights are updated.

In our experiments, the forward pass was repeated for several iterations over the whole train set, also called epochs. After each epoch, the models got tested in the validation phase by means of their accuracy and loss with respect to the true labels (samples) of the validation set. This was done both to verify models’ performances as training steps increased, in order to avoid overfitting, and to check for the optimal parameters as different hyper-parameter configurations were tested. In this study, for the hyper-parameter selection, we tried different configurations by choosing from the most common parameters in the literature. More specifically the hyperparameters were chosen among the following list:

- Batch size: 16, 32.
- Learning rate (Adam): 5e-5, 3e-5, 2e-5, 1e-5.
- Number of epochs: 2, 3, 4, 5.

The best configurations resulting from the training phase are reported in the table below. In addition, during training, a linear scheduler was created, with no warmup steps, to linearly decrease the learning rate to 0 as the training steps increased. Moreover, we applied gradient clipping to prevent the “exploding gradient” problem. Each training phase lasted approximately 5 minutes. For having more insights on the training procedure, the python script that we used for fine-tuning the UmBERTo pre-trained model for Automatic Misogyny Identification is publicly available on Google Colaboratory⁷.

Model	Batch	Learning rate	Epochs
AIBERTo	16	1e-5	4
GilBERTo	16	2e-5	4
UmBERTo	16	1e-5	5

Table 3: configuration parameters adopted for fine-tuning the models. The parameters were selected by means of their performances on the validation set.

Results

All the models were trained in 5 different runs and their performances were tested at each run with respect to the labelled testing set released from the Ami Evalita 2018 evaluation campaign. All models

⁷ <https://colab.research.google.com/drive/10n62gthRy7xX5qoWbkmPER1fpVWK0bJE?usp=sharing>

were evaluated with respect to their accuracies when predicting labels for the test set. The table below reports, for all the models, the mean of their accuracies with their standard deviation, as well as the raw accuracies of the baseline algorithm and of the most accurate model evaluated on the campaign.

	mAc	SD
AIBERTo	0.864	0.005
GilBERTo	0.862	0.008
UmBERTo	0.865	0.002
	Accuracy	
Bakarov.c.run2	0.844	
AMI-BASELINE	0.83	

Table 4: Mean accuracy and standard deviation of each model. The data was sampled across 5 different runs. The table also reports the accuracy of the AMI Evalita 2018 baseline and of the most accurate model.

All the models, with similar training procedures, reached similar performances. However, it is important to mention that the fine-tuned models based on UmBERTo show, on average, the highest accuracy rates, while those based on GilBERTo show the lowest. Since the two language models were pre-trained on a similar corpus (CommonCrawl ITA) and with similar training procedures, this difference could be due, maybe, to the fact that the first is a cased language model, while the second is uncased. In fact, it can be easily pointed out how uppercase words may often convey a different sentiment than their respective lowercase form. In addition, this can also explain the better performances that UmBERTo reached, with respect to AIBERTo, the only model pre-trained on a social-media language corpus.

Finally, it is notable that all our models outperformed the systems evaluated in the Ami Evalita 2018 campaign. The most accurate system evaluated, *bakarov.c.run2*, was outperformed by an average increasing, with respect to its accuracy rate, of 1,97%; with respect to the baseline our models are averagely more accurate of 3,36%.

Conclusions

In this report we talked about BERT and the shared task of Automatic Misogyny Identification for Italian, as proposed by Fersini et al. in the Ami Evalita 2018 campaign. Furthermore, we reported how we fine-tuned three different pre-trained BERT language models for Italian, AIBERTo, GilBERTo and UmBERTo for solving the task of identifying misogynous content. Their performances were evaluated, across different runs, with respect to their accuracies on the same

dataset of the shared task. Following our results, all the models outperformed the systems evaluated in the 2018 campaign. This allows us to promote these BERT models as state-of-the-art tools in the solution of AMI problems and, more generally, the BERT architecture as one of the most promising solutions for text classification in deep learning. In future it would be interesting to see how these models behave in different tasks, such as multi-label classification, or to see how the results of these fine-tuned models may improve by integrating their predictions with lexical or semantic information.

References

- Amir Bakarov. 2018. Vector Space Models for Automatic Misogyny Identification. In *Proceedings of Sixth Evaluation Campaign of Natural Language Processing and Speech Tools for Italian. Final Workshop (EVALITA 2018)*, Turin, Italy. CEUR.org.
- Valerio Basile, Mirko Lai, and Manuela Sanguinetti. 2018. Long-term social media data collection at the university of turin. In *Fifth Italian Conference on Computational Linguistics (CLiC-it 2018)*, pages 1– 6. CEUR-WS.
- Yoshua Bengio, Réjean Ducharme, Pascal Vincent, Christian Jauvin. 2003. A Neural Probabilistic Language Model. In *Journal of Machine Learning Research 3*, pages 1137–1155.
- Tommaso Caselli, Nicole Novielli, Viviana Patti, and Paolo Rosso. 2018. EVALITA 2018: Overview of the 6th Evaluation Campaign of Natural Language Processing and Speech Tools for Italian. In Tommaso Caselli, Nicole Novielli, Viviana Patti, and Paolo Rosso, editors, *Proceedings of Sixth Evaluation Campaign of Natural Language Processing and Speech Tools for Italian. Final Workshop (EVALITA 2018)*, Turin, Italy. CEUR.org.
- Jacob Devlin, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee, and Kristina Toutanova. 2019. BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers)*, pages 4171–4186, Minneapolis, Minnesota, June. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Elisabetta Fersini, Maria Anzovino, and Paolo Rosso. 2018a. Overview of the task on automatic misogyny identification at IberEval. In *Proceedings of the Third Workshop on Evaluation of Human Language Technologies for Iberian Languages (IberEval 2018)*. CEUR Workshop Proceedings. CEUR-WS. org, Seville, Spain
- Elisabetta Fersini, Deborah Nozza, and Paolo Rosso. 2018b. Overview of the evalita 2018 task on automatic misogyny identification (ami). In *Proceedings of the 6th evaluation campaign of*

Natural Language Processing and Speech Tools for Italian. Final Workshop (EVALITA 2018), Turin, Italy. CEUR.org.

- Yinhan Liu, Myle Ott, Naman Goyal, Jingfei Du, Mandar Joshi, Danqi Chen, Omer Levy, Mike Lewis, Luke Zettlemoyer, and Veselin Stoyanov. 2019. Roberta: A robustly optimized BERT pretraining approach. ArXiv preprint 1907.11692.
- Tomas Mikolov, Ilya Sutskever, Kai Chen, Greg S Corrado, and Jeff Dean. 2013. Distributed representations of words and phrases and their compositionality. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 26*, pages 3111–3119. Curran Associates, Inc.
- Matthew Peters, Mark Neumann, Mohit Iyyer, Matt Gardner, Christopher Clark, Kenton Lee, and Luke Zettlemoyer. 2018a. Deep contextualized word representations. In *NAACL*.
- Marco Polignano, Pierpaolo Basile, Marco de Gemmis, Giovanni Semeraro and Valerio Basile. 2019. ALBERTo: Italian BERT Language Understanding Model for NLP Challenging Tasks Based on Tweets. In *Proceedings of the Sixth Italian Conference on Computational Linguistics (CLiC-it 2019)*, Bari, Italy. CEUR.org.
- Adriane Van Der Wilk. 2018. Cyber Violence and Hate Speech Online Against Women: Women's Rights & Gender Equality: Study for the FEMM Committee. European Parliament.
- Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N Gomez, Lukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. 2017. Attention is all you need. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, pages 6000–6010.